

Supplementary Table 1: Locality Data

Geographic coordinates and distribution, key to site codes, identification of strata sampled at each locality.

Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Submembers Sampled	Depositional Environment
AA-1449 (AA)	38.58	-83.70	Harpers Run, Stony Hollow creek, Middle Clarksville	Deep Subtidal
Apricot Lane (AL)	38.33	-83.77	Bon Well Hill, Harpers Run, Stony Hollow Creek, Middle Clarksville	Shallow Subtidal + Deep Subtidal
Flemmingsburg 32-bypass (FB)	38.40	-83.72	Bon Well Hill, Harpers Run, Stony Hollow Creek	Shallow Subtidal
Moore's Branch (MB)	Private Property	Private Property	Middle Clarksville	Deep Subtidal
Stony Hollow Creek (SH)	39.40	-83.98	Stony Hollow Creek, Middle Clarksville	Offshore
Dollar General (DG)	38.12	-83.75	Stony Hollow Creek, Middle Clarksville	Shoal
Bon Well Hill (BH)	39.43	-84.98	Bon Well Hill, Stony Hollow Creek	Offshore
South Gate Hill (SG)	39.33	-84.95	Bon Well Hill, Stony Hollow Creek	Offshore
Decatur Outcrop (DO)	38.81	-83.68	Bon Well Hill, Harpers Run, Stony Hollow Creek, Middle Clarksville	Deep Subtidal
Caesar's Creek (CC)	39.47	-84.06	Bon Well Hill, Harpers Run, Stony Hollow Creek, Middle Clarksville	Offshore
Hoffman Falls (HF)	38.75	-85.42	Bon Well Hill, Harpers Run, Stony Hollow Creek	Offshore